

ISic4410

Fragmentary Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2019.09.09

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Aquae Segestanae

Place of origin (modern)

Terme Segestane

Provenance

Among material recovered from the territory of Partinico, in this case ascribed to Terme Segestane

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Partinico, Biblioteca Comunale/Antiquarium Comunale

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble plaque, of which part of the upper border is preserved with a simple moulding, but broken on left, right and below.

Dimensions

Height not currently recorded cm

Width not currently recorded cm

Depth not currently recorded cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Latin letters, with a moulding above

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Deeply incised elegant, v-cut letters, with pronounced serifs and comma-shaped interpuncts. The letters are very regularly proportioned and neatly cut, fairly closely spaced, and with faint guidelines top and bottom.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: not currently recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not currently recorded mm

Text

1. [---]N · F · F[---]

2. [---]V[---]

Apparatus

Text based on photograph

No trace is visible before the initial N, but some blank space is preserved; the final letter is most likely an I

The initial letter is either an O or a Q

Translation (en)

Commentary

Believed to be unpublished; full autopsy still required.

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4410>

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Bibliography

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Photo M. Metcalfe